

A Compendium to the Phosphoregulation of Mitosis

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Introduction:

Mitosis is largely driven by the highly ordered process of phosphorylation and dephosphorylation. Current estimates from large scale deep phosphor-proteomics analysis suggest that the majority of the proteasome is fully-phosphorylated during mitosis, highlighting the extensive network of events that phosphorylation controls. To better understand these events, we utilised the unique Minardo layout, which displays multi-dimensional information including time which flows around a schematic "circuit" cell (Ma et al., 2013). Over 90 events are visually represented on the layout, providing a quick yet comprehensive overview of the key phosphorylation events that regulate entry, progression and exit from mitosis (Burgess et al., 2017). Each phosphorylation event is visually linked to its upstream regulatory kinase or phosphatase, adding an additional layer of information. In addition, the website version (<http://www.cell.com/cell/enhanced/odonoghue2>), is fully interactive allowing users to click on each phosphosite, with the pop-up box containing direct links to 3D structure, UniProt and most importantly, a simple description along with additional phosphorylation events and direct links to the supporting literature in PubMed. Currently, the information contained within these pop-up boxes is not easily accessible or searchable, limiting its use, consequently in this review we have re-compiled the pop-up boxes to enable easy access to the information and provide a comprehensive compendium of the major phosphorylation events currently known to be essential for mitosis.

1. Late G2, Mitotic Kinase Activation at the Centrosome

Phosphorylation of AURKA on T-288 by AURKA:

T-288 is an auto-phosphorylation site on AURKA. Phosphorylation of this site is proposed to occur by intermolecular auto-phosphorylation of long-lived dimer pairs (Bayliss et al., 2003; Ohashi et al., 2006; Zhang et al., 2012; Zorba et al., 2014). However, recent results with an AURKA FRET biosensor suggest that T-288 auto-

phosphorylation can occur through intramolecular mechanisms (Bertolin et al., 2016). Phosphorylation of T-288 on AURKA may also involve nucleophosmin (NPM), which is a strong activator of AURKA at centrosomes, inducing S-89 auto-phosphorylation and AURKA activity independent of T-288 phosphorylation (Reboutier et al., 2012). T-288 phosphorylation is removed by the phosphatase PP6, which interacts with AURKA through BRCA1, when phosphorylated by Chk2 on S-988. AURKA can prevent PP6 mediated inhibition by phosphorylating BRCA1 on S-308 during mitosis, preventing its binding to AURKA (Ertych et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of CDC25B on S-353 by AURKA

CDC25B is phosphorylated on S-353 at centrosomes by AURKA, which is believed to activate CDC25B allowing initial dephosphorylation of centrosomal CDK1 on Y-15. Removal of Y-15 by CDC25B triggers CDK1 activity and the entry to mitosis. Activated CDK1 freely shuttles between the nucleus and cytoplasm (Dutertre et al., 2004; Cazales et al., 2005). The related CDC25A is also phosphorylated by CDK complexes during G2 on S-283, which helps to promote mitotic entry (Mazzolini et al., 2016).

De-phosphorylation of CDK1 on Y-15 by CDC25B

CDC25B is a dual-specific phosphatase that dephosphorylates CDK1 on Y-15 and T-14 resulting in the activation of a pool of CDK1/cyclin B at centrosomes during G2 (Poon et al., 1996; De Souza, Colin P.C., Ellem & Gabrielli, 2000; Lindqvist et al., 2005). Centrosomal pools of Cyclin A/CDK2 are implicated in activating CDC25B resulting in downstream activation of CDK1 (Mittra & Enders, 2004; De Boer et al., 2008). Additionally, Cyclin A/CDK2 binds and phosphorylates APC/CDC20 during interphase, blocking APC/CDC20 activity, thereby allowing accumulation of Cyclin A2 and B1 and timely mitotic entry (Hein & Nilsson, 2016).

Phosphorylation of BORA on S-41 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of S-41 by CDK1 (along with S-112 and S-137) blocks BORA degradation, promoting BORA association with PLK1, which is required for subsequent AURKA activation of PLK1 (Thomas et al., 2016). PLK1 activation by AURKA-BORA is required for mitotic entry (Seki et al., 2008), while DNA damage interrupts the interaction between AURKA and BORA thereby resulting in inhibition of PLK1 and G2 arrest (Bruinsma et al., 2017).

Phosphorylation of PLK1 on T-210 by AURKA

Phosphorylation of PLK1 on T-210 by AURKA-BORA activates PLK1 kinase activity, with small amounts of AURKA-BORA required for continual PLK1 activation during mitosis. This activation appears to function as a bistable switch ensuring robust PLK1 activity once a cell has committed to entering mitosis (Bruinsma et al., 2014). AURKA-BORA activation of PLK1 is also required for recovery from G2 checkpoint arrest (Macůrek et al., 2008).

Phosphorylation of AURKB on T-232 by AURKB

During late S/early G2 phase the chromosomal passenger complex (CPC), including AURKB, is recruited to pericentromeric heterochromatin regions via INCENP, which binds to HP1. This restricts S-10 phosphorylation on HIST1H3A to centromeric regions (Cooke, Heck & Earnshaw, 1987; Monier, Mouradian & Sullivan, 2007; Nozawa et al., 2010). INCENP is able to partially activate AURKB, resulting in auto-phosphorylation of T-232 (Yasui et al., 2004).

Phosphorylation of CEP192 on T-44 by PLK1

CEP192 binds AURKA and PLK1 targeting them to centrosomes where they are activated. PLK1 then phosphorylates CEP192 on T-44 and several additional residues creating binding sites for the γ -tubulin ring complex. This phosphorylation may also attract additional pericentriolar material components thereby driving microtubule nucleation, centrosome maturation and mitotic spindle assembly (Joukov, Walter & De Nicolo, 2014).

Phosphorylation of NDEL1 on S-251 by AURKA

AURKA phosphorylates NDEL1 at S-251, which is required for centrosome targeting of TACC3. This phosphorylation is essential for centrosome separation and maturation during mitotic entry (Mori et al., 2007). AURKA also phosphorylates CPAP on S-467 throughout mitosis, starting from prophase. This phosphorylation is required to ensure that spindle pole integrity is maintained throughout mitosis (Chou et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of CCNB1 on S-147 by PLK1

PLK1 phosphorylates S-147 and several additional sites (S-126, S-128, S-133) on cyclin B1 (CCNB1), which block nuclear export of CCNB1, leading to the accumulation CDK1/CCNB1 in the nucleus (Toyoshima-Morimoto et al., 2001; Jackman et al., 2003; Santos et al., 2012). CCNB1 and B2 are both commonly over-expressed in cancer causing aneuploidy by inhibition of separase and AURKA-mediated PLK1 hyperactivation, respectively (Nam & van Deursen, 2014)

2. Prophase, Chromosome Condensation Begins

Phosphorylation of CDC25C on S-214 by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylates CDC25C on multiple sites (T-48, T-67, S-122, T-130, S-168, S-214), which blocks the inhibitory S-216 phosphorylation required for 14-3-3 protein binding, thereby allowing CDC25C to activate CDK1 (Bulavin et al., 2003; Bagheri-Yarmand et al., 2010).

Dephosphorylation of CDK1 on Y-15 by CDC25C

CDC25C removes Y-15 phosphorylation on CDK1, which is required to fully activate CDK1 and maintain the auto-amplification loop during mitosis (Karlsson et al., 1999; Lorca et al., 2010; Trunnell et al., 2011; Potapova et al., 2011).

Phosphorylation of NCAPD3 on T-1415 by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylates NCAPD3 on T-1415, creating a consensus polo box domain. PLK1 is recruited to this domain, phosphorylating additional sites on the condensin II complex (Ono et al., 2004; Abe et al., 2011).

Phosphorylation of CENPA on S-68 by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylates the histone H3 variant CENPA at S-68 during mitotic entry, preventing CENPA binding to the assembly factor HJURP. CDK1 also phosphorylates M18BP1, which along with HJURP helps restrict CENPA assembly at centromeres to G1 phase (Müller et al., 2014; Stankovic et al., 2017; Pan et al., 2017). Phosphorylation of CENPA at S-68 has been proposed to prevent CENPA loading into centromeric chromatin until late telophase (Yu et al., 2015). However, recent evidence suggests S-68 phosphorylation may not be essential for centromere deposition or function (Fachinetti et al., 2017). CENPA is also phosphorylated on S-7 by AURKA during prophase, which promotes enrichment of AURKB at inner centromeres and correct kinetochore function (Kunitoku et al., 2003). CENPA recruits CENPT, with subsequent phosphorylation of CENPT on T-11, T-85, and S-201 by CDK1 promoting the recruitment of NDC80C and MIS12C, which are members of the KMN outer kinetochore complex (Huis in 't Veld et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of CASC5 on T-875 by TTK

T-875 is located in one of the MELT sequences on CASC5 (KNL1), which is a member of the KMN outer kinetochore complex. Phosphorylation of T-875 along with additional sites within the MELT sequences by TTK (Mps1) creates binding sites for BUB1, which then phosphorylates Histone H2A. The BUB1/KNL1 axis ensures highly efficient kinetochore microtubule attachment. T-875 is specifically targeted by PP2A-B56 during spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) silencing (Nijenhuis et al., 2014; Vleugel et al., 2015). PLK1 also phosphorylates KNL1 and TTK, enhancing TTK activity and the recruitment of MAD1/C-MAD2 and BUB3/BUBR1 to kinetochores (Schubert et al., 2015)

Phosphorylation of ECT2 on T-373 by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylation of ECT2 at T-373 (T-341 human iso2) promotes ECT2 translocation from the nucleus to the cytoplasm and activation of RhoA mediated cell rounding. Phosphorylation at T-373 also inhibits ECT2 activity, which is relieved by binding to RacGAP1 at the membrane and prevents ECT2 relocalisation to mid-zone. CDK1 also phosphorylates ECT2 at T-444, which creates a binding site for PLK1 (Hara et al., 2006; Niiya et al., 2006). CDK1 and AURKA also promote cell rounding during prophase by phosphorylating ARHGEF2 (GEF-H1), which prevents RhoA activation before anaphase (Birkenfeld et al., 2007). Finally, CDK1 promotes cell rounding by reducing focal adhesion during mitotic entry directly phosphorylating integrins, focal adhesion kinase (FAK) and paxillin (Yamakita et al., 1999; Robertson et al., 2015).

Phosphorylation of BUB1 on T-589 by BUB1

BUB1 auto-phosphorylation of T-589 during interphase primes its kinase activity allowing subsequent BUB1 phosphorylation of histone H2A on T-120 at centromeric regions. This promotes BUB1 recruitment of shugoshin (SGO1) and PP2A, which protects cohesin at centromeres until the metaphase–anaphase transition (Asghar et al., 2015).

Phosphorylation of HIST1H2AI on T-120 by BUB1

T-120 phosphorylation of HIST1H2AI promotes the recruitment of shugoshin (SGO) proteins and creates a binding site for PP2A-B56 to localise to the centromere. This localisation is required to protect centromeric cohesin from removal during prophase (Tang et al., 2004b; Kawashima et al., 2010; Liu, Jia & Yu, 2013; Asghar et al., 2015).

Phosphorylation of CDCA8 on multiple sites by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylates T-106 and a cluster of 6 consensus sites (T-171, T-185, T-189, T-199, T-204 and S-219) in the C-terminal domain of CDCA8 (borealin). This promotes chromosome passenger complex (CPC) binding to the coiled-coil region of shugoshin (SGO), which is in turn targeted to centromeres by interacting with centromeric nucleosomes only when histone H2A is phosphorylated by BUB1 (Tsukahara, Tanno & Watanabe, 2010).

Phosphorylation of ESPL1 on S-1126 by CDK1

ESPL1 (separase) is phosphorylated by CDK1 at S-1126, promoting binding between separase and cyclin B1 (CCNB1). This inhibits both separase and CDK1 (Gorr, Boos & Stemmann, 2005). CDK1 also phosphorylates Pin1, which promotes the isomerization of separase at the metaphase-to-anaphase transition, a process that prevents its re-inhibition by residual securin and limits the half-life of separase proteolytic activity to anaphase (Hellmuth et al., 2015).

Phosphorylation of INCENP on T-892 by AURKB

AURKB binds INCENP partially activating AURKB, allowing subsequent AURKB mediated phosphorylation of INCENP at T-892, which forms part of a conserved Thr-Ser-Ser (TSS) motif near the C-terminus of INCENP. This is followed by the auto-phosphorylation of AURKB on its activation loop, which elicits full kinase activity (Honda, Körner & Nigg, 2003; Yang et al., 2009; Xu et al., 2010).

Phosphorylation of AURKB on T-232 by AURKB

Auto-phosphorylation on T-232 corresponds to the kinase activation loop (T-loop) of AURKB, which must be phosphorylated to fully activate AURKB kinase (Yasui et al., 2004; Sessa et al., 2005). T-232 is dephosphorylated by PP2A, which binds AURKB through the tumour suppressor protein CYLD (Sun et al., 2010).

Phosphorylation of H2AFX on S-121 by AURKB

AURKB-mediated phosphorylation of H2AFX at S-121 provides a platform for the activation of AURKB (auto-

phosphorylation of T-232). This site contributes to the positive feedback of AURKB activation and is essential for proper chromosome segregation (Shimada et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of GSG2 on T-128 by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylates GSG2 (Haspin) on T-128 creating a binding site for PLK1, which further phosphorylates GSG2 on its N-terminus, relieving the auto-inhibition of GSG2 activity (Ghenoiu, Wheelock & Funabiki, 2013; Zhou et al., 2014).

Phosphorylation of GSG2 on multi-sites by PLK1

PLK1 phosphorylates multiple sites (including S-151, S-221 and S-349) on the N-terminus of GSG2 (haspin), activating GSG2 kinase activity to phosphorylate histone H3 at T-3. Phosphorylation of T-3 is required for the recruitment of AURKB and chromosomal passenger complex (CPC) to chromatin (Ghenoiu, Wheelock & Funabiki, 2013; Zhou et al., 2014).

Phosphorylation of GSG2 on S-93 by AURKB

AURKB phosphorylates GSG2 (haspin) *in vitro* on (S-93, S-108, S-143), but may phosphorylate up to 11 sites in total. This phosphorylation helps promote a positive feedback loop involving haspin and AURKB, which promotes chromosome passenger complex (CPC) accumulation at centromeres and phosphorylation of histone H3 on T-3 (Wang et al., 2011).

Phosphorylation of PPP1R7 on S-24 by PLK1

Phosphorylation of PPP1R7 (protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 7, also known as SDS22) by PLK1 at S-24, S-27, S-44, S-47 and T-277 strengthens the binding of PPP1R7 to PP1 and inhibits the dephosphorylation of T-232 on AURKB ensuring correct AURKB function at kinetochores (Duan et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of CDCA2 on S-591 by CDK1

CDCA2 (repo-Man) is a protein scaffold that enables phosphatase signalling at mitotic chromosomes. During prophase-prometaphase, CDK1 phosphorylation at S-591 reduces the binding of PP1 to Repo-Man, facilitating the recruitment of PP2A-B56 and centromeric localization of AURKB, which then phosphorylates Repo-Man on S-893. CDK1 also phosphorylates S-400, T-412 and T-419 (Qian et al., 2013; 2015). Loss of CDK1 activity during anaphase results in a switch from PP2A-B56 to PP1 recruitment (Vagnarelli et al., 2011).

Phosphorylation of MASTL on T-194 by CDK1

The T-194 phosphorylation site is located within a region on MASTL homologous to a kinase activation loop (T-loop). Phosphorylation of T-194 by CDK1 during mitotic entry is required for MASTL kinase activity (Blake-Hodek et al., 2012; Hégarat et al., 2014).

Phosphorylation of HIST1H3A on T-3 by GSG2

GSG2 phosphorylates HIST1H3A on T-3 facilitating the condensation and resolution of chromatids. T-3

phosphorylation also promotes AURKB and chromosomal passenger complex (CPC) enrichment at centromeres, allowing the phosphorylation of HIST1H3A on S-10 (Dai et al., 2005; Kelly et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2010; Wilkins et al., 2014).

Phosphorylation of HIST1H3A on S-10 by AURKB

AURKB phosphorylation of HIST1H3A at S-10 is required for the correct condensation of chromosomes (Hsu et al., 2000). This site directs HST2P to deacetylate HIST1H4A at K-16 (HIST1H4A K16). Removing this acetyl group allows neighbouring nucleosomes to bind together, promoting chromosome condensation (Wilkins et al., 2014). Phosphorylation of HIST1H3A on S10 by AURKB also results in a dissociation of HP1 from chromatin, especially from pericentromeric (arm) regions helping to promote chromosome arm resolution (Hirota et al., 2005; Fischle et al., 2005).

3. Centrosome Separation and Mitotic Spindle Formation

Phosphorylation of NEK9 on S-869 by CDK1

CDK1 acts as a priming kinase by phosphorylating NEK9 at S-869. This phosphorylation recruits PLK1, which then phosphorylates additional sites, activating NEK9 (Bertran et al., 2011).

Phosphorylation of NEK9 on T-210 by PLK1

PLK1 binds to and phosphorylates NEK9 on T-210, a site which corresponds to the kinase activation loop (T-loop) on NEK9 (Bertran et al., 2011). NEK9 phosphorylates several downstream targets including NEDD1 (S-377), which drives NEDD1 and γ -tubulin recruitment to the centrosome (Sdelci et al., 2012). In addition, the C-terminus of NEK9 is able to bind to and activate NEK7 by releasing the auto-inhibitory effects of Y-97 phosphorylation on NEK7, a process that is independent of NEK9 kinase activity (Haq et al., 2015). NEK9 plays critical roles in regulating centrosome separation and spindle formation, with loss of NEK9 inducing severe mitotic defects (Kaneta & Ullrich, 2013), which can block the proliferation of p53 null cancer cells (Kurioka et al., 2014).

Phosphorylation of KIF11 on S-1033 by NEK9

In human cells, NEK9 activates NEK6/7 which then phosphorylates KIF11 (EG5) on S-1033 promoting its localization to centrosomes, where it is later required for driving centrosome separation. KIF11 is also phosphorylated by CDK1 at T-926 (Blangy et al., 1995; Smith et al., 2011; Bertran et al., 2011). The phosphatase PTEN negatively regulates phosphorylation of KIF11 (EG5) during mitosis, with loss of PTEN resulting in hyper-phosphorylation of EG5 preventing its recruitment to the mitotic spindle, leading to short, aberrant mitotic spindles and chromosome segregation defects (He et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of NEDD1 on S-377 by NEK9

NEK9 phosphorylates NEDD1 on S-377 driving it and γ -tubulin to the centrosome, where they are necessary for correct maturation of centrioles and nucleation of microtubules (Gomez-Ferrera et al., 2012; Sdelci et al., 2012). NEK9 binds to and activates NEK7 kinase (Haq et al., 2015) promoting recruitment of pericentriolar material (PCM) proteins required for correct centriole duplication and spindle pole formation (Kim, Kim & Rhee, 2011). In response to DNA damage during mitosis, NEK7 interacts with and phosphorylates TRF1 on S-114, stabilizing TRF1 at telomeres, thereby protecting them from further damage (Tan et al., 2017).

Phosphorylation of STK3 on S-15 by PLK1

STK3 (serine/threonine-protein kinase 3, also known as MST2) phosphorylates Nek2A kinase at S-15 with the assistance of the scaffold protein hSav1. This phosphorylation is crucial for the formation of the hSav1–NEK2A–STK3 complexes and the targeting of phosphorylated NEK2A to centrosomes (Mardin et al., 2011). NEK2 then phosphorylates C-Nap1 on multiple sites, which perturbs both oligomerization and CEP135 interaction, promoting centrosome disjunction at the onset of mitosis (Hardy et al., 2014).

4. Nuclear Envelope Breakdown and Inhibition of Phosphatase Activity

Phosphorylation of PP1 on T-320 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of T-320 by CDK1 inhibits PP1 phosphatase activity. This site is auto-dephosphorylated by PP1 during early anaphase (Wu et al., 2009; Grallert et al., 2015).

Phosphorylation of NPC on multi-sites by CDK1

The nuclear pore complex (NPC) is made up of around 1000 different subunits. Multiple nuclear pore proteins (NUPs) are phosphorylated by CDK1 and additional kinases, which trigger NPC disassembly (De Souza, Colin P.C. et al., 2004). Examples include NUP50 (S-221) (Kosako et al., 2009), NUP98 (T-548, T-553, S-653, T-670, reported as T-529, T-539, S-595, S-623 by Laurell et al.) (Laurell et al., 2011) and NUP210 (S-1881, reported as S-1880 by Favreau et al.) (Favreau et al., 1996). Summary of NPC breakdown reviewed by (Smoyer & Jaspersen, 2014; Álvarez-Fernández & Malumbres, 2014).

Phosphorylation of MASTL on S-875 by MASTL

The C-terminal S-875 phosphorylation of MASTL is a possible auto-phosphorylation site (Blake-Hodek et al., 2012) required for full activation of MASTL kinase activity (Vigneron et al., 2011). MASTL activity along with CDK1 is required for CRM1 mediated nuclear export of MASTL just prior to nuclear envelope breakdown (Wang et al., 2013; Álvarez-Fernández et al., 2013).

Phosphorylation of ENSA on S-67 by MASTL

Phosphorylation of ENSA at S-67 and the related protein ARPP19 at S-62 by MASTL significantly increases their affinity for PP2A-B55, where they act as 'unfair' competitive inhibitors by occupying the active site of the PP2A-B55 complex (Gharbi-Ayachi et al., 2010; Mochida et al., 2010; Williams et al., 2014; Mochida, 2014). In starfish oocytes, ARPP19 is phosphorylated on S-106 by MASTL and S-69 by CDK1, with the latter creating a novel bypass mechanism that is sufficient for CDK1-cyclin B autoregulatory activation (Okumura et al., 2014). Finally, the PP2A-B55/MASTL/ENSA pathway in combination with CDK1 is both necessary and sufficient for creating the bistable switch-like phosphorylations required for mitotic entry (Mochida et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of LMNB1 on S-23 by CDK1

Lamin B1 is phosphorylated on S-23 by CDK1 and several additional sites with the aid of PKC. These phosphorylations help drive nuclear envelope disassembly during nuclear envelope breakdown, with complete disassembly occurring by metaphase (Mall et al., 2012).

5. Prometaphase and The Spindle Assembly Checkpoint

Phosphorylation of HIST1H3A on T-118 by AURKA

AURKA phosphorylates HIST1H3A (Histone H3) on T-118 at pericentromeres and chromosome arms during prophase but is lost upon chromosome alignment. This phosphorylation is suggested to occlude cohesin and condensin complexes from the DNA, giving the condensed chromatid increased conformational flexibility that is required for microtubule attachment (Wike et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of CDCA5 on T-159 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of CDCA5 (sororin) at T-159 by either CDK1 or PLK1 destabilizes the interaction between PDS5A and sororin. Removal of sororin from cohesin complexes allows WAPL to bind PDS5A, this exchange of proteins promotes the removal of cohesin, specifically from the chromosome axes during prophase (Nishiyama et al., 2013; Liu, Jia & Yu, 2013).

Phosphorylation of CASC5 on S-24 by AURKB

CASC5 (KNL1) phosphorylation on S-24 by AURKB inhibits the binding of PP1 to the kinetochore. This ensures that the spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) signal is not silenced prematurely (Welburn et al., 2010; Nijenhuis et al., 2014). AURKB also phosphorylates Mis12C (Kim & Yu, 2015), Dam1 and Ndc80 (Kalantzaki et al., 2015).

Phosphorylation of CDC20 on S-153 by BUB1

BUB1 directly phosphorylates CDC20 at S-153, providing a scaffold for subsequent PLK1-mediated phosphorylation of CDC20 at S-92, with both

phosphorylation events required for efficient inhibition of CDC20 (APC/C-CDC20) in vitro and correct checkpoint signalling in human cells (Tang et al., 2004a; Jia, Li & Yu, 2016).

Phosphorylation of BUB1 on T-609 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of T-609 by CDK1 localizes BUB1 to the kinetochore and creates a polo-binding domain (PBD), which recruits PLK1. BUB1 acts as a scaffold allowing PLK1 to phosphorylate CDC20, this is one of 2 pathways used to inhibit CDC20 (APC/C-CDC20) function prior to mitotic exit (Qi, Tang & Yu, 2006; Jia, Li & Yu, 2016).

Phosphorylation of CDC20 on S-92 by PLK1

BUB1 and PLK1 act in parallel to directly inhibit CDC20 (APC/C-CDC20) function (Jia, Li & Yu, 2016). S-92 phosphorylation by PLK1 prevents delivery of the E2 ubiquitin-activating enzyme UBE2S to the APC/C. Removal of S-92 by PP2A-B56 stabilizes kinetochore-microtubule attachments and shuts off the spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) (Craney et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of BUB1B on S-676 by PLK1

Phosphorylation of BUB1B (BUBR1) on T-620 by CDK1 triggers the recruitment of PLK1, which further phosphorylates BUBR1 at S-676. This promotes stability of kinetochore-microtubule (KT-MT) interactions, timely mitotic progression, and chromosome alignment at the metaphase plate (Elowe et al., 2007; Lera et al., 2016). Efficient recruitment of PLK1 to kinetochores during prometaphase is dependent on NCAPG2, a component of the condensin II complex (Kim et al., 2014b).

Phosphorylation of BUB1 on S-670 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of S-670 on BUB1B (BUBR1) by CDK1 is important for microtubule-kinetochore attachment sensing (Elowe et al., 2009). Specifically, S-670 phosphorylation recruits PP2A-B56 phosphatase to improperly attached kinetochores where it counteracts AURKB kinase (Kruse et al., 2013; Nijenhuis et al., 2014). S-670 remains phosphorylated during early mitotic exit (McCloy et al., 2015). BUBR1 in conjunction with MAD2, BUB3 and CDC20 forms the Mitotic Checkpoint Complex (MCC), which is essential for spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) function. BUBR1 contains two conserved ABBA motifs that bind and help rapidly inhibit active APC/C-CDC20 (Di Fiore et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of STAG2 on S-1224 by PLK1

Phosphorylation of STAG2 (cohesin subunit SA-2) at S-1224 by PLK1 promotes the dissociation of cohesin II from the chromatin arms during prophase and prometaphase (Hauf et al., 2005).

Phosphorylation of AURKB on S-331 by CHK1

CHK1 phosphorylates AURKB at S-331 to ensure full AURKB kinase activity during prometaphase (Petsalaki et al., 2011).

6. Attachment, Correction and Alignment of Chromosomes by the Mitotic Spindle

Phosphorylation of KIF18A on S-684 by CDK1

KIF18A is phosphorylated by CDK1 at S-674 and S-684, which facilitates chromosome movements during prometaphase/early metaphase (Häfner et al., 2014).

Dephosphorylation of AURKA on T-288 by PP1

AURKA is dephosphorylated on T-288 when localized at mitotic spindles, most likely by PP1 which removes this site in vitro (Walter et al., 2000; Satinover et al., 2004). However, binding of TPX2 to dephosphorylated AURKA is sufficient to re-activate AURKA kinase activity (Dodson & Bayliss, 2012; Zorba et al., 2014).

Phosphorylation of TACC3 on S-558 by AURKA

Phosphorylation of TACC3 on S-558 by AURKA is required for its spindle localization (LeRoy et al., 2007). AURKA-dependent control of the TACC3/ch-TOG/clathrin axis is proposed to control spindle length, stability and speed of spindle formation (Lin, Hu & Shih, 2010; Burgess et al., 2015). AURKA also phosphorylates several other important regulators of mitotic spindle assembly including GM130 (Wei et al., 2015), NUSAP1, and MAP7 (Sardon et al., 2010).

Phosphorylation of MAPRE3 on S-176 by AURKA

AURKA phosphorylation of the microtubule end binding protein MAPRE3 (EB3) at S-176 triggers disruption of the EB3-SIAH-1 complex, resulting in EB3 stabilization during mitosis (Ban et al., 2009). Additionally, the related EB1 and EB2 proteins are also phosphorylated by AURKB and CDK1, with these phosphorylations critical for correct temporal regulation of EB1/2. Together phosphorylations of the EB family regulate microtubule binding, kinetochore-microtubule dynamics, and spindle orientation (Ferreira et al., 2013; Iimori et al., 2016). AURKA also phosphorylates NUMA on S-1969, which is regulated the spindle orientation and positioning functions of NUMA during metaphase (Gallini et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of TPX2 on T-369 by MAPK

The T-369 site on TPX2 is a consensus motif for and potentially phosphorylated by CDK1/MAPK (Wittmann et al., 2000; McCloy et al., 2015; Petrone et al., 2016). TPX2 plays important roles in regulating mitotic spindle length and microtubule flux. Rapid dephosphorylation of T-369 by PP2A-B55 during early mitotic exit is required to release importin- α from TPX2, which subsequently allows TPX2 to localize to the central-spindle. Failure to dephosphorylate T-369 results in aberrant nuclear import (Cundell et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of INCENP on T-59 by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylation of INCENP at T-59 is required for PLK1 recruitment to kinetochores during prometaphase (Goto et al., 2006) with the PLK1/AURKB/INCENP complex

playing crucial roles in the regulation of chromosomal attachment to the mitotic spindle (Carmena et al., 2012). CDK1 phosphorylation of INCENP is also important for preventing binding with KIF20A (Mklp2), and thereby restricting relocalization of the chromosome passenger complex (CPC) to the central-spindle in anaphase (Hümmer & Mayer, 2009; Vázquez-Novelle & Petronczki, 2010; Kitagawa et al., 2014). CDK1 also phosphorylates 6 sites (T-478, S481, T507, T524, S798, T807) within the C-Terminal SAH domain of INCENP. These phosphorylations disrupt MT-binding and promote SAC silencing (Wheelock et al., 2017).

Phosphorylation of TPX2 on T-72 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of TPX2 at T-72 by CDK1 negatively regulates TPX2 association with the mitotic spindle, preventing over-activation of AURKA at the spindle, which can cause abnormally elongated spindles, likely due to increased KIF11 (EG5) activity (Shim et al., 2015).

Phosphorylation of BIRC5 on T-34 by CDK1

BIRC5 (survivin) is a component of the chromosomal passenger complex (CPC), which includes AURKB. BIRC5 is required for sustained spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) arrest in response tension loss (Lens et al., 2003). Phosphorylation at T-34 by CDK1 (Fortugno et al., 2002) blocks caspase-9 mediated mitotic cell death (O'Connor et al., 2000). During a prolonged mitotic arrest, CDK1 also phosphorylates XIAP on S-40 and MCL-1 on T-92, blocking their anti-apoptotic functions and priming cells for mitotic cell death (Harley et al., 2010; Hou, Allan & Clarke, 2017)

Phosphorylation of CDCA8 on T-230 by TTK

CDCA8 (borealin), is a member of the chromosome passenger complex (CPC) that regulates the AURKB. CDCA8 is directly phosphorylated by TTK (Mps1) on T-230 activating AURKB during error correction and chromosome alignment (Jelluma et al., 2008; Bourhis et al., 2009). Dimerization of CDCA8 is also important for correct CPC and spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) functioning (Bekier et al., 2015).

Phosphorylation of KIF2C on T-95 by AURKB

AURKB phosphorylates T-95 on KIF2C (MCAK), simultaneously localizing KIF2C to the centromere, and inhibiting its microtubule depolymerizing activity. However, PLK1 phosphorylation of S-715 on KIF2C balances AURKB inhibition. This crucial balance between inhibition and activation is essential to allow KIF2C activity to correct improper kinetochore-microtubule attachments (Andrews et al., 2004; Shao et al., 2015).

Phosphorylation of PRC1 on T-481 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of the non-motor protein PRC1 at T-481 (and T-470) by CDK1 during prometaphase and metaphase, negatively regulates PLK1 binding, preventing the localization of PLK1 to the spindle microtubules. These CDK1 phosphorylations are critical to maintain

mitotic progression and spindle bipolarity prior to anaphase onset (Neef et al., 2007; Cundell et al., 2013). PRC1 modulates correct spindle formation by binding to and blocking RacGAP1 inhibition of CDC42, which is required for mitotic spindle formation (Ban et al., 2004). In addition, during metaphase PRC1 acts as a 'bridging fibre' linking non-kinetochore microtubules with the outermost sister kinetochore fibre (k-fibre) to help balance inter kinetochore tension (Kajtez et al., 2016; Polak et al., 2017).

7. The Metaphase to Anaphase Transition

Phosphorylation of APC1 on S-313 by CDK1

CDK1 is recruited to hyper-phosphorylated APC3 where it phosphorylates the associated APC1 at S-313 (S-314 in *X. laevis*), and several additional sites within the N-terminal loop region (S-317, S-334, S-341, S-355, S-377, S-386, which correspond to S-318, S-335, S-344, S-358, S-380 and S-389 in *X. laevis*). These phosphorylations promote the loading of CDC20 into the APC/C, thereby activating its ubiquitylation ligase activity required for the degradation of mitotic substrates such as cyclin B1 (CCNB1), which results in a reduction in CDK1 activity (Zhang et al., 2016; Qiao et al., 2016; Fujimitsu, Grimaldi & Yamano, 2016).

Phosphorylation of KIF18A on S-684 by PP1

Dephosphorylation of KIF18A at S-684 by PP1 during metaphase, results in metaphase plate thinning, and reduces the oscillatory movements of chromosomes (Häfner et al., 2014).

Phosphorylation of CLASP2 on S-1034 by PLK1

CLASP2 is phosphorylated by CDK1 on S1013, recruiting PLK1, which then phosphorylates S-1034 on human CLASP2. This helps to stabilize kinetochore-microtubule attachments, maintain spindle bipolarity and align chromosomes at the metaphase plate. Note that Maia et al. report the S-1013 site as S-1234 and S-1034 as S-1255 (Maia et al., 2012). CLASP2 is also phosphorylated by GSK3 during mitosis, this phosphorylation inhibits the MT-binding activity of CLASP2 α , thereby weakening kinetochore-microtubule (KT-MT) interactions. GSK3 mediated phosphorylations are proposed to help spatially and temporally control KT-MT interactions thereby ensuring correct chromosome segregation (Pemble et al., 2017).

Phosphorylation of TPX2 on S-121 by AURKA

AURKA phosphorylation of TPX2 at S-121 during metaphase is necessary for maintaining correct spindle length after the spindle reaches its steady state during metaphase (Fu et al., 2015).

Phosphorylation of RAD21 on S-454 by PLK1

RAD21 (SCC1 homolog) is a cleavable component of the cohesin complex. Phosphorylation of RAD21 at S-454 by

PLK1, primes the adjacent R-450 site for cleavage by ESPL1 (separase). Cohesin cleavage dissolves the connection between sister chromatids, allowing chromosome segregation in anaphase (Alexandru et al., 2001; Hauf et al., 2005; Agircan & Schiebel, 2014; Lin, Luo & Yu, 2016).

Dephosphorylation of CASC5 on S-24 by PP2A-B56

CASC5 (KNL1) is dephosphorylated on S-24 by PP2A-B56, which reveals an RVSF motif, a known PP1 consensus binding site. This site recruits PP1-gamma to the kinetochore, where it promotes the disassembly of the KNL1/BUB1 complex (Welburn et al., 2010; Nijenhuis et al., 2014). PP1 is also recruited to kinetochores during metaphase by the spindle- and kinetochore-associated (Ska) complex. The role of PP1 at kinetochores is to promote anaphase progression by silencing SAC kinase signalling (Sivakumar et al., 2016).

Auto-dephosphorylation of PP1 on T-320

PP1 auto-dephosphorylates itself at T-320 as CDK1 activity begins to drop during late metaphase, concomitant with cyclin B degradation, resulting in an increase in PP1 phosphatase activity (Wu et al., 2009; Grallert et al., 2015).

Dephosphorylation of MASTL on multi-sites by PP1

MASTL is rapidly dephosphorylated by PP1 as cells exit mitosis (M-A transition) on CDK1-directed threonine sites (likely T-194, T-207, T-741) (Hégarat et al., 2014; Rogers et al., 2016) and on S-875 (in *X. laevis*) (Heim, Konietzny & Mayer, 2015; Ma et al., 2016). FCP1 has also been implicated in dephosphorylation of MASTL during mitotic exit (DellaMonica et al., 2015). Inactivation of MASTL allows subsequent reactivation of PP2A-B55, which in turn likely completes the dephosphorylation and inactivation of MASTL during mitotic exit. Loss of MASTL function results in the rapid dephosphorylation of TTK (Mps1), by PP2A-B55, which deactivates TTK kinase activity and silences the spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) (Diril et al., 2016).

Dephosphorylation of HIST1H3A on T-3 by PP1

PP1 initiates the decondensation of the mitotic chromatin by the dephosphorylation of T-3 on HIST1H3A (Histone H3), which may also help AURKB to re-localize to the central-spindle during mitotic exit (Qian et al., 2011; Afonso et al., 2014). Lagging or misaligned chromosomes are rapidly phosphorylated on S-31 of Histone H3.3 during anaphase, which persists into G1, triggering a p53 dependent response that blocks proliferation of aberrantly divided cells (Hinchcliffe et al., 2016).

Dephosphorylation of CASC5 on T-875 by PP1

The T-875 phosphorylation site on CASC5 (KNL1) is located within one of the ~19 MELT sequences used by BUB1 to bind KNL1. Dephosphorylation of T-875 and the surrounding MELT sequences disassembles the mitotic checkpoint complex (MCC) and turns off spindle assembly

checkpoint (SAC) signalling (Nijenhuis et al., 2014; Vleugel et al., 2015).

Dephosphorylation of CDC20 on S-41 by PP2A-B55

Phosphorylation of CDC20 at S-41 (S-50 in *X. laevis*) is required for inhibition of the APC/C (Chung & Chen, 2003). Dephosphorylation of CDC20 by PP2A-B55 may be crucial for APC/C activation after spindle assembly checkpoint silencing (Cundell et al., 2016).

Dephosphorylation of CDCA5 on T-159 by PP2A-B55

CDCA5 (sororin) is phosphorylated on T-159 by AURKB and CDK1 in vitro and this phosphorylation promotes its release from chromatin in mitosis (Dreier, Bekier & Taylor, 2011; Nishiyama et al., 2013). This site is dephosphorylated by PP2A-B55 (Cundell et al., 2016). PP2A also dephosphorylates sororin, which helps protect centromeric cohesin from cleavage until the metaphase-anaphase transition (Liu, Rankin & Yu, 2013; Hara et al., 2014).

8. Mid-Spindle Formation during Anaphase-Telophase

Dephosphorylation of PRC1 on T-470 by PP2A-B55

Dephosphorylation of T-470 by PP2A-B55 is required for subsequent phosphorylation of the non-motor protein PRC1 by PLK1. This dephosphorylation enhances the microtubule bundling activity of PRC1 at the central-spindle (Cundell et al., 2013; 2016).

Dephosphorylation of TPX2 on T-369 by PP2A-B55

TPX2 is phosphorylated at T-369 by AURKA. Rapid dephosphorylation of this site by PP2A-B55 is required for the timely localisation of TPX2 to the central-spindle during anaphase (Cundell et al., 2016).

Phosphorylation of PRC1 on S-601 by PLK1

PRC1 is phosphorylated on S-601 and T-602 by PLK1 (Neef et al., 2007; Hu et al., 2012). Phosphorylation of T-481 during mitosis promotes the dephosphorylation of T-602 by PP2A. Dephosphorylation of T-481 during early anaphase, releases this inhibition, allowing PLK1 to phosphorylate S-601/T-602 promoting central-spindle localisation and bundling of microtubules (Cundell et al., 2013; 2016).

Phosphorylation of RacGAP1 on S-157 by PLK1

PLK1 phosphorylation of RacGAP1 (MgcRacGAP) at S-157 is required for the recruitment of ECT2 to the central-spindle where it promotes RhoA activity and cleavage furrow formation (Burkard et al., 2009; Wolfe et al., 2009). Efficient ECT2 binding also requires phosphorylation of the nearby S-164 site by PLK1 (Kim et al., 2014a). Correct furrow formation requires ECT2 localisation to the plasma membrane (Kotýnková et al., 2016) and is also dependent on the phosphorylation of Anillin at S-635 by an unknown kinase (Kim et al., 2017)

Dephosphorylation of ARHGEF2 on S-959 by PP2A-B55

Dephosphorylation of S-959 increases the guanine nucleotide exchange activity of ARHGEF2 (GEF-H1). This increased activity allows GTP loading of RhoA, which is required for cleavage furrow formation (Birkenfeld et al., 2007). S-959 is a proline directed site with a lysine (basic) residue at the +5 position, implicating PP2A-B55 as the potential phosphatase. In support, S-163 on GEF-H1 is dephosphorylated by PP2A-B55 (Cundell et al., 2016)

9. Nuclear Envelope Reformation

Dephosphorylation of NUP107 on T-46 by PP2A-B55

NUP107 is rapidly dephosphorylated during mitotic exit on multiple sites (McCloy et al., 2015) with T-46 dephosphorylated in a PP2A-B55 dependent manner (Cundell et al., 2016). Dephosphorylation of NUP107 promotes binding with ELYS/Mel28, which recruits lamin-B receptor (LBR) during nuclear envelope reformation during telophase (Clever et al., 2012).

Dephosphorylation of POM121C on S-246 by PP2A-B55

POM121C is dephosphorylated on multiple sites during mitotic exit, but to a lesser extent than NUP107 (McCloy et al., 2015) with S-246 on POM121C dephosphorylated in a PP2A-B55 dependent manner (Cundell et al., 2016). POM121C is recruited to the re-forming nuclear pore complex after NUP107 (Bodoor et al., 1999; Antonin et al., 2005).

Dephosphorylation of NUP153 on S-257 by PP2A-B55

NUP153 is required for timely progression through late mitosis (Mackay, Elgort & Ullman, 2009). Failure to recruit NUP153 to chromosomes activates an AURKB-mediated abscission checkpoint (Mackay, Makise & Ullman, 2010). Multiple phosphorylation sites on NUP153 must be removed for correct recruitment, with S-257 site removed by PP2A-B55 (Cundell et al., 2016). However, Repo-Man (a PP1 subunit) is responsible for recruiting NUP153 to chromosomes during late anaphase/telophase in a PP1-independent manner (Vagnarelli et al., 2011).

Dephosphorylation of NUP98 on T-553 by PP2A-B55

NUP98 is hyper-phosphorylated by multiple kinases including CDK1 and the NEK family of kinases during mitotic entry (Laurell et al., 2011) with removal of these phosphorylation necessary for efficient reassembly of the nuclear pore during mitotic exit. NUP98 is recruited concomitantly with NUP93 to chromatin during mitotic exit (Dultz et al., 2008) with the T-553 site dephosphorylated in a PP2A-B55 dependent manner (Cundell et al., 2016). NUP98 also plays an important role in preventing APC/C(Cdh1)-mediated ubiquitination of securin prior to anaphase (Jeganathan, Malureanu & van Deursen, 2005). NUP98 fusion oncoproteins, which are found in a variety of cancers including AML (Struski et al., 2017), cause premature mitotic exit and aneuploidy (Salsi et al., 2014) by binding to APC/CDC20 and disrupting its

function. Phosphorylation of NUP98 on S-606 regulates its binding to APC/CDC20 (Salsi, Fantini & Zappavigna, 2016).

Dephosphorylation of LMNB1 on multi-sites by PP1

AKAP149 recruits PP1 at the nuclear envelope (NE) upon nuclear reformation in vitro, and PP1 targeting to the NE is a prerequisite for assembly of B-type lamins (Thompson, Bollen & Fields, 1997; Steen et al., 2000). LMNB1 is concentrated around chromosomes during telophase and is recruited after Lamin-B receptor (LBR), NUPs and POM121C (Moir et al., 2000; Clever et al., 2012). The exact phosphosites targeted by PP1 are unknown but LMNB1 is highly phosphorylated during mitosis, with T-20 and S-28 significantly dephosphorylated during mitotic exit (McCloy et al., 2015).

10. Telophase - Chromatin Decondensation and Cleavage Furrow Formation

Phosphorylation of AURKB on S-331 by CLK1,2,4

CLK1, CLK2 and CLK4 localize to the midbody in an interdependent manner, associate with and phosphorylate AURKB on S-331, this action completes AURKB activation in telophase (Petsalaki & Zachos, 2016). AURKB activity mediates the abscission checkpoint during cytokinesis to monitor for unsegregated chromatin at the cleavage site and prevent tetraploidization caused by furrow regression (Steigemann et al., 2009). AURKB and ULK3 phosphorylate members of the ESCRT-III complex preventing abscission (Carlton et al., 2012; Thoresen et al., 2014; Caballe et al., 2015).

Phosphorylation of INCENP on S-894 by LATS1/2

INCENP and AURKB operate in a positive feedback loop through the Thr-Ser-Ser (TSS) motif on INCENP. Phosphorylation of S-894 within the TSS motif by LATS1/2 initiates the positive feedback with AURKB, essential for the completion of cytokinesis (Yabuta et al., 2016).

Dephosphorylation of HIST1H3A on S-10 by PP1

PP1 is responsible for the dephosphorylation of S-10 on HIST1H3A (Histone H3) during mitotic exit (Hsu et al., 2000; Murnion et al., 2001), which re-establishes the binding of HP1 to chromatin and HIST13AH3 K-9 methylation. The binding of HP1 proteins is critical for the formation of heterochromatin regions, which regulate chromosome organisation and gene expression during the subsequent interphase (Fischle et al., 2005). In addition, PP1-RepoMan also dephosphorylates S-28 on HIST1H3A promoting possible methylation of H3K27, which combined with HP1 binding contributes to the re-establishment of heterochromatin regions. The binding of PP1-RepoMan to NUP153 helps restrict heterochromatin to the nuclear periphery (de Castro et al., 2017).

Phosphorylation of RacGAP1 on S-387 by AURKB

During late telophase AURKB phosphorylates RacGAP1 (MgcRacGAP) on S-387 at the midbody switching on GAP activity. Active RacGAP1 binds to, and inactivates RhoA at the contractile ring to complete cytokinesis (Minoshima et al., 2003).

Dephosphorylation of RacGAP1 on S-157 by PP2A-B56

The LxxIxE motif of RacGAP1 (MgcRacGAP) mediates recruitment of PP2A-B56 to the central-spindle, where it dephosphorylates RacGAP1 at S-157 and ensures efficient cytokinesis. This phosphatase recruitment may oppose PLK1 at the midbody, helping to maintain tight control over RacGAP1 activity (Touré et al., 2008; Kim et al., 2014a; Hertz et al., 2016).

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